

Experience of Foreign Bodies in Aerodigestive tract at Tertiary care Centre in Eastern Nepal

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Abstract:

Background:

Foreign Bodies (FB) in aerodigestive tract pose a big diagnostic and therapeutic challenge to the otorhinolaryngologists. FBs in air passage are commonly seen in younger children while FB in food passage is encountered both in children and adults. This study is about the experience of aerodigestive FBs at a tertiary-care hospital.

Objective:

To study the incidence, types, management and complications of foreign bodies encountered in the aerodigestive tract.

Materials and Methods:

This was a prospective study done in the Department of ORL and Head and Neck surgery, BPKIHS Dharan for a period from August 2016 to October 2018.

Result:

There were a total of 396 foreign bodies managed by Department of ORL and Head and Neck Surgery. Out of which 354 were in digestive tract and 42 in respiratory tract. Bone, especially the chicken bone was the commonest foreign body ingested. However, in children, coin was the most common FB ingested. Seeds were the commonest FBs inhaled. Cricopharynx was the most common site of FB lodgment in the digestive tract while right main bronchus was the commonest site of lodgment of inhaled FB.

Conclusion:

FBs in aerodigestive tract is a challenging emergency for otorhinolaryngologists. FB in airway is life-threatening and should be managed immediately. Rigid oesophagoscopy and bronchoscopy are the treatments of choice for aerodigestive tract FBs with excellent outcome.

Key Words:

Foreign body, aerodigestive tract, chicken bone, coin

Ear, nose and throat specialists treatment challenges

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Abstract:

The purpose and objective of Tie Up with hospitals around the globe is to help medicate the impact of ENT specialists shortage in these third world country.

Zambia, in Southern Africa in a landlocked country of rugged terrain and diverse wildlife with many natural game Parks and safari areas. On its borders with Zimbabwe is famed Victoria Falls-indigenously called Mosi-oa-Tunya or "Smoke that Thunders" Plunging a misty 108m despite being a beautiful country. Zambia faces problems just like any developing country. One of the issue that can be highlighted and is peculiar to Zambia possibly alone in Sub-Saharan Africa, is how it lacks availability of ENT specialists. It has a population of 17.9million (worldometers _ www.worldometers.info/) against 8 ENT specialist Doctors. The majority of these people reside in the rural areas.

The lack of ENT specialist in health Care center, is compounded by inadequate or inefficient basic equipment much as those used in Ear examination, Nose examination

Tonsillectomy, Adenoidectomy, Oesphagoscope, Laryngoscope, in both urban and rural areas. Everything used is improvised, also non availability of well-defined training for the following categories of health Care givers, Doctors, Medical Licentiate, Clinical Officers, Nurses, and perhaps ENT community health Care givers. Therefore does not offer patients with the best outcome in the attempt to improvement there quality of life.

COMMON CONDITIONS

The following are the common ones in Zambia;

1. Chronic adenoiditis affects children from 3 - 12 years which will require adenoidectomy
2. Chronic tonsillitis in same case combined with Adenoiditis and needs Adeno-tonsillectomy
3. Throat irritation (feeling obstruction or feeling of a foreign body in the throat) due to a long uvular which may require excision.
4. Middle Ear fluid which may require draining of fluid and inserting glommet.
5. Chronic Otitis media which may require tympanoplasty.
6. Acquired hearing loss due to chronic ear infections, Cerebral malaria, Meningitis and occupational hazard eg noise induced hearing loss from major industries which may require Audiometry testing which may resulting in the need of hearing aids.

In an ideal setup the conditions above can be well managed with 100 percent good prognosis, however, Zambia lacks a deal setup therefore generating the idea of hospital partnership or Tie-up.

The 17.9million people live in 10 different provinces are all referred to one man hospital; The University Teaching hospital - UTH which is found in the capital city for most ENT cases that needs specialists treatment against 8 ENT specialist as stated earlier comprises of both local and expatriate Doctors. 7 are at the University Teaching hospital and 1 in Livingstone which is the tourist capital of Zambia. These does not begin to provide basic primary health care for the population especially because majority of the population are vulnerable and depending on developing government of the support. Currently very few people are privileged enough to be in medical health scheme however, the government is in the process of assisting the under privileged by introducing medical health insurance for all citizens.

Finally Morning Rise Private Clinic attempts to medicate ENT specialist shortage for over 4million this requires assistance from cooperating partners in equipment, training and voluntary work in public and private partnership the government. Therefore consider having a conference in this part of the world for more excitement.

Complete Autologous Solutions for Reconstruction of Hearing Mechanisms

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Abstract:

Since ages, several methods of ossicular re-construction and cavity-less mastoid surgery have been reported. The ultimate aim is the serviceable hearing and a near normal physi-ology. The presentation highlights the techniques for use of autologous materials for different types of ossicular chain defects and cavity free surgery with the help of animations and short videos on power point.

Methods: - Patients of chronic otitis media presenting with different types of ossicular defects were repaired with new techniques of ossiculoplasty (including autologous total and partial ossicular replacement prosthesis) using autologous grafts materials along with techniques of cavity free surgery for squamous type of Otitis Media. Post-operative evaluation was performed at 3 months by oto-endoscopy and audiogram at 0.5, 1, 2 and 3KHz and compared.

Results: - Successful rehabilitation of pure tone average to 30 dB or less was achieved in more than 85 per cent of the patients and dry near physiologically functioning postopera-tive external auditory canal was achieved in 98 per cent of the patients.

Conclusion: - The micro-surgical techniques demonstrated in the presentation, using au-tologous graft materials for different types of ossicular defects as described in Austin's classification, can cost effectively maximize the gains in terms of biocompatibility, stability, magnetic resonance imaging compatibility and hearing. Cavity-less surgeries can add to the above results giving almost a physiologi-cally functioning ear.

Key Words:

Ossiculoplasty, tympanoplasty, ossicles, mas-toidectomy, cavity obliteration, total ossicular replacement prosthesis, partial ossicular replacement prosthesis.

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|-----------------------|-----------------|
| 1. Facial Nerve | 2. Oval window |
| 3. Promontory | 4. Pyramid |
| 5. Tympanomeatal flap | 6. Round window |

Figure 1: Figure illustrating transcanal microscopic and cross sectional view of how complete ossicu-lar chain disruption can be repaired using autologous total ossicular replacement prosthesis.

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Endoscopic Sinus Surgery at Al Diwanyia Teaching Hospital, Overview

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Abstract:

Background and Objectives

This is a retrospective analysis of 200 patients who underwent endoscopic sinus surgery (ESS) at Al Diwanyia teaching hospital in Diwanyia city, Iraq , from August 2016 – August 2018 (24 months) which demonstrate indication for surgery, challenges, complications, follow up , and out come .

Patients and Methods:

200 patients with age range from 17-59 years with chronic rhinosinusitis without nasal polyposis (CRSsNP) (160) , chronic rhinosinusitis with nasal polyposis (CRSwNP) (30 patients) , and patients with Allergic fungal rhinosinosis (AFRS) (10 patients). All the patients underwent endoscopic sinus surgery under general anesthesia after trial of medical treatment . The outcome of surgery is identified in the 3 categories of patients, complications of surgery and causes of failure. The follow up period range from 7-24 months. The success rate defined by disappearing the signs and symptoms of rhinosinusitis. The success of surgery defined by disappearance of symptoms (VAS) and endoscopic findings postoperatively.

Result:

The success rate was 95% (152) in CRSsNP, 80% (24) in CRSwNP and 90% (9) in AFRS. Complications (overall) was in the form of severe bleeding in 4% , orbital ecchymosis in 6% , orbital fat prolapse in 3% , adhesion in 9% , no major complications were occurred. The success of surgery depend on proper operative technique, early postoperative debridement, ensure good and proper nasal douching with proper pre and postoperative medications.

Conclusions:

Endoscopic sinus surgery is a safe with high success rate just if surgeon is well trained with the main principles with backup, good results associated with good follow up , and the best way to avoid complications by training and more training .

Biography:

Wasam A. Albusalih had been graduated from college of medicine in Baghdad 1999, Degreed in Otorhinolaryngology Head and neck surgery in 2013 , interested much in endoscopic sinus surgery since that , I did more than 100 successful DCR and about 500 endoscopic sinus operations with few endoscopic skull base operations in last 3 years at Diwanyia, Iraq.

Larynx And Pharynx: Making Ent Easy With Easy Sketch Diagram And Our Very Own Hand Model

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Abstract:

To make ENT subject easy to understand and explain to students, doctors as well as patients I have created easy sketch diagrams and using our very own hand models to demonstrate and understand better. Almost all parts of ear, nose throat as been made easy. Larynx, Pharynx, Nose, Sinuses, Whole ear, Facial nerve....etc.
This lecture on the topic mentioned above will be an easy way not only learn but also to teach anyone.

Biography:

I, Dr. D. Vijayagovindarajan, completed my undergraduation (MBBS) and post-graduation (Diploma in Otorhinolaryngology) from Bangalore university, Sri Devaraj Urs Medical college, Karnataka, India.

Later joined Government Vellore medical college, Tamilnadu as a honorary tutor for 10 years and was teaching students "MAKING ENT EASY WITH SKETCH DIAGRAMS AND HAND MODELS". This teaching started making people call me to take lectures throughout India at state, zones, national and even international (France) conferences.

I also started my very rural practice to take this speciality of medicine ENT to the needy there for very minimal cost.